

Supporting Information

A Versatile Luminescent Ga-Organic Framework with Multi-emission Centers as a Blue LED and Fluorescent Probe for Low-temperature Detection and Selective Fe³⁺ Sensing

Wei-Wei Shi ¹, Lei Liang ¹, Jin-Ping Zhang ², Hai-Han Ye ², Xin-Cheng Hu ², Jian-Wei Zhang ^{2,*} and Wei Wei ²

¹ School of Petrochemical Engineering, Liaoning Petrochemical University, Fushun 113001, Liaoning, P. R. China; shiweiwei1980@163.com (W.-W.S.); liangleikyxb@163.com (L.L.)

² **Henan Engineering Center of New Energy Battery Materials**, School of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering, Shangqiu Normal University, Shangqiu 476000, Henan, P. R. China; jijj3j@163.com (J.-P.Z.); yehaihan824@163.com (H.-H.Y.); huxincheng2019@163.com (X.-C.H); weiweizzuli@163.com (W.W.)

* Correspondence: jwzhang85@163.com (J.-W.Z.)

1. Materials and Methods.

Reagents: All reagents and solvents were purchased from commercial sources without further purification. The organic ligand biphenyl-3,4',5-tricarboxylic acid (H₃PTC, 97%) were purchased from CHEMSOON Co., Ltd (Shanghai, China). Ga(NO₃)₃·xH₂O (99.9%), Sc(NO₃)₃·xH₂O (99.99%), DMF (N,N-dimethylformamide, 99.5%) and HAC (acetic acid, 99.5%) were purchased from Aladdin Industrial Inc (Shanghai, China). NaNO₃ (AR), KNO₃ (AR), Cd(NO₃)₂·4H₂O (AR), Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (AR), Zn(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (AR), Mg(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (AR), Al(NO₃)₃·9H₂O (AR), Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O (AR), Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (AR), EtOH (ethanol, AR), Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O (AR), BaSO₄ (AR) and KBr (AR) were purchased from Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd (Shanghai, China).

Characterization: Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) pattern was collected by a Rigaku MiniFlex600 diffractometer with Cu K α ($\lambda = 1.54056 \text{ \AA}$, 40 kV, 15 mA) at room temperature by 0.02° steps. FT-IR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Tensor 27 spectrophotometer using KBr pellets in the range of 4000–400 cm⁻¹. The UV-vis absorption spectra measured on a Hitachi U-3900 UV/vis spectrophotometer using BaSO₄ pellets in the range of 700–200 nm at room temperature. The temperature-dependent luminescent measurements were recorded a Horiba FluoroMax+ spectrofluorometer. The solid-state photoluminescence properties and metal ions sensing were recorded on Hitachi F-7100 fluorescence spectrophotometer at room temperature.

Figure S1. The Rietveld refinement XRD pattern of as-synthesized SNNU-63.

Figure S2. FT-IR spectra of the organic ligand and SNNU-63.

Figure S3. Excitation and emission spectra of the free H₃PTC ligand.

Figure S4. Excitation and emission spectra of SNNU-63.

Figure S5. The solid-state UV-Vis absorption spectra of SNNU-63 and the free H_3PTC ligand at room temperature.

Figure S6. The corresponding CIE 1931 chromaticity diagram of SNNU-63 at room temperature.

(a)

(b)

Figure S7. Comparison of photo for SNNU-63 under the natural light (a) and UV 254 nm light (b).

Figure S8. Excitation and emission spectra of SNNU-63 MOF aqueous suspension.

Figure S9. Luminescence intensity ($I_{382 \text{ nm}}$) of SNNU-63 to different metal ions in aqueous (0.4 mM) under excitation of 288 nm.

Figure S10. Fluorescence quenching of SNNU-63 dispersed in aqueous solutions of twelve different metal cations (0.4 mM).

Figure S11. Linearity relationship of luminescent intensity of SNNU-63 and Fe³⁺ ion at low concentrations.

Figure S12. The reversibility and recyclability of SNNU-63 based on the maximum emission intensity at 382 nm in water (1 mL 2 mg/mL) in the presence of 2 mL 0.6 mM aqueous solution of Fe³⁺ ions.